

ESFRI Position

on Considering the Scientific Interest of
Radio Astronomy in the Regulatory
Framework for Sharing the Use of the
6425-7125 MHz Frequency Band

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Position Paper

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With this statement ESFRI urges the Radio Spectrum Committee to consider the scientific interests of Radio Astronomy in the regulatory framework for radio spectrum in the Upper 6GHz.

The European Strategic Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) represents the Research Ministries of all EU Member States and Associated Countries¹. ESFRI is supporting an integrated system of European Research Infrastructures to strengthen the strategic European autonomy in research and innovation. The Research Infrastructures enable world-class science, innovation and maintain a breeding ground for talented researchers and engineers. Such an ecosystem also enables private partners to stay closely connected to innovations in technologies and instrumentation. The socio-economic impact of Research Infrastructures cannot be underestimated.

The Research Infrastructures were built with pooled resources from European partners. The research infrastructures are embedded in extensive European collaborations and national nodes, forming the backbone of a (global) distributed research and innovation ecosystem². The infrastructure lifecycle spans over 40 years and the international networks and ecosystems developed over decades. This was all achieved through the long-term investments from the European institutions and Ministries.

European public investment in major radio astronomy infrastructure is easily exceeding several billions of Euros. The European VLBI Network (EVN), the SKA Observatory, and the European Southern Observatory's Atacama Large Millimeter/submillimeter Array (ALMA) alone represent strategic long-term investments that underpin Europe's leadership in astronomy and astrophysics. Their value extends far beyond scientific discovery, delivering technological innovation, industrial and workforce development, and broader societal benefits through education and international cooperation.

The Upper 6 GHz band is of critical importance to not just current but also future European and international radio astronomy infrastructures: it contains naturally occurring emissions from specific molecules in interstellar space, allowing astronomers to study how stars form and how gas moves within our Milky Way galaxy. In particular the emission from Methanol provides unique information on the formation of high-mass stars. Signals in this band are extremely faint, so maintaining a clean, interference-free environment is essential for obtaining accurate measurements. Access to the Upper 6 GHz window therefore supports high-quality observations that deepen our understanding of the structure and evolution of the universe, with major discoveries currently being made, and

¹ <https://www.esfri.eu/about>

² https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/fostering-research-infrastructure-ecosystems-for-addressing-complex-scientific-and-societal-challenges_34797721-en.html

further breakthroughs to be expected. It will be central to upcoming joint observations between the EVN and the SKA-Mid.

Based on CEPT Report 92, sharing the band 6650–6675.2 MHz between the radio astronomy service and WBB-ECS (wireless broadband-electronic communications services) will be complex and difficult to achieve. Large coordination areas would be required, with radii of at least 350 km in flat open terrain. Depending on the envisaged coordination procedures, the potential burden on Radio Astronomy Services (RAS) sites will be significant. Assigning the band to WBB-ECS, without introducing an appropriate regulatory framework that can sufficiently ensure radio astronomy observations, will have grave consequences for research in astronomy. In [annex I](#) additional technical information is provided.

Not preserving the 6650–6675.2 MHz frequency range to radio astronomy will have a negative socio-economic impact, representing a systemic risk to European research capacity. The consequences for the sustainability of the European Radio Astronomy infrastructures and European competitiveness will be irrevocable, and the long-term investments (as mentioned above) will not yield.

Taking into account the already limited spectrum resources available to European Astronomy Observatories, we urge the RSC to minimise the impact as described above and to consider appropriate and balanced solutions. Any regulatory framework should remain practical and proportionate for scientific facilities, supporting the leading role of Europe in global astronomy.

ANNEX I

Additional technical information

The technical compatibility studies summarized in CEPT Report 92, strongly indicate that sharing of the band 6650–6675.2 MHz between the radio astronomy service and WBB-ECS (wireless broadband-electronic communications services) will be difficult to achieve. While the report concludes that co-channel sharing with WBB ECS may be feasible when mitigation techniques are applied within a site-specific coordination framework, minimum separation distances (which we understand as coordination distances) will be required. Moreover, the various studies resulted in a very wide range of distances, owing to the very different assumptions applied in the technical studies by different stakeholders. It should be stressed that if existing (3.6-GHz) IMT antenna installations were to be augmented with WBB ECS equipment in the upper 6-GHz band, the assumption used in some studies that 100 % of base stations are affected by significant clutter³ will not be realistic in several countries. It is also important to note that not all mitigation measures may be feasible in every context. For example, when existing antenna masts are reused, an adaptive use of local clutter is not feasible. This is also a consequence of coverage requirements, as antenna masts are strategically deployed to minimise exposure to local clutter and maximise the service area. Likewise, reducing the transmitted power or modifying the antenna sector pointing directions may require a complementary strategy (e.g. use of alternative IMT bands or deployment refinement) to fill the resulting coverage gaps. Thus, although there is certainly the possibility for deployment of WBB-ESC in many European areas, significant coordination or even exclusion zones around RAS sites would be necessary.

To minimise the impact the Coordination areas should at least have a radius of about 100 km if observatories are well shielded via natural terrain (e.g., Effelsberg, Germany), and up to 350 km if they are in more open and flat terrain (e.g., Torun in Poland, Westerbork in NL).

Depending on the envisaged coordination procedures, the potential burden on RAS sites could be significant. A tiered approach could be feasible, where certain measures (e.g., beam avoidance or reduced transmit power) are applied broadly and only at certain closer distances some level of case-by-case treatment is envisaged. Furthermore, safeguarding mechanisms should be established to allow issues to be addressed even after operating permits have been granted for WBB-ESC installations, should cases of harmful interference be reported.

For adjacent-band compatibility, the required separation distances presented in CEPT Report 92 are considerably smaller. Nevertheless, the principles outlined above should still be applied, on an appropriately reduced scale.

³ Physical obstructions in the radio link between transmitter and receiver in a compatibility study.

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